

The classical definition of a Jew refers to someone who is simultaneously granted Jewish faith and Jewish lineage. And Jewish faith, traditionally, means believing in the Abrahamic covenant. And to believe in the covenant, one must traditionally believe in the existence of God. This is because a covenant is a contract, and a contract is reciprocal. I cannot make a contract with myself, nor with a stone or a doll. Even if such contracts existed, they wouldn't be contracts because there's no external compulsion. Now, a significant number of Jews argue that belief in Judaism, or more precisely, belief in the existence of God, does not define a Jew.

"Humanistic Judaism is a non-theistic, human-centered movement that stresses human agency and rejects the idea of a higher, or supernatural, power that affects, guides or in any way controls human life, or did so at any time in history."

"Since the movement does not believe in God, the liturgy of Humanist Judaism does not use any theistic language." "Humanistic Judaism accepts intermarriage, defining as Jews those who identify with the history, culture, and future of the Jewish people." (Encyclopedia of Judaism)

If that's the case, then who are Jews? According to their claims, they are people who belong to the tradition of following Jewish law. But then, what is that tradition? If one doesn't believe in the existence of God, the covenant is meaningless. And the tradition of Judaism is fundamentally not about superficialities, but about what Jews promised through the covenant with God. Jews observed Hanukkah and abstained from pork not for their ethnic identity, but to uphold their covenant with God, and that observance was their Jewish identity. Therefore, this Jewish identity is the covenant with God. However, the moment God is rejected, that tradition ceases to function as any tradition at all. This is because as long as it's observed purely out of preference and not as a contract, it can no longer maintain the covenant, and those past Jews are no longer Jews. That's why ancient Jews expelled Christians, because they refused to observe the law.

And they also expelled Spinoza because he denied a personal God who makes covenants. So, the moment God is denied, all Jewish traditions lose their meaning. So let's try to redefine tradition: let's say Judaism is merely a set of gestures with no connection to inner belief. In that case, now everyone can legitimately become a Jew. Suppose an American observes all Jewish festivals, all restrictions, and is circumcised. However, he is a Muslim and has not changed his beliefs at all: he merely follows Jewish traditions. But since your Judaism has no faith-based element, he is now a legitimate Jew. Should we call him a brother now? If you refuse, you are certainly a hypocrite and have not even adhered to the Judaism

you redefined. In that case, you might redefine Judaism as having both Jewish tradition and Jewish lineage. Yes, a Jew is a blood-related ethnic group sharing a common paternal ancestor. In that case, Palestinians are potential brothers, because modern genetic research shows they share specific common genes with other Jews, distinct from people of other countries, and are genetically closer than people from other countries. "Besides Southern European groups, the closest genetic neighbors to most Jewish populations are the Palestinians, Bedouins, and Druze. The observed differentiation of these groups reflects their histories of within-group endogamy. Yet, their genetic proximity to one another and to European and Syrian Jews suggests a shared genetic history of related Middle Eastern and non-Semitic Mediterranean ancestors who chose different religious and tribal affiliations." (Abraham's Children in the Genome Era: Major Jewish Diaspora Populations Comprise Distinct Genetic Clusters with Shared Middle Eastern Ancestry) "The comparison with other Mediterranean populations by using neighbor-joining dendrograms and correspondence analyses reveal that Palestinians are genetically very close to Jews and other Middle East populations, including Turks (Anatolians), Lebanese, Egyptians, Armenians, and Iranians. Archaeologic and genetic data support that both Jews and Palestinians came from the ancient Canaanites, who extensively mixed with Egyptians, Mesopotamian, and Anatolian peoples in ancient times. Thus, Palestinian-Jewish rivalry is based in cultural and religious, but not in genetic, differences." (The Origin of Palestinians and Their Genetic Relatedness With Other Mediterranean Populations)

Most of them are direct descendants of ancient Jews. So you would say they can't be Jews because they are Muslims. But what's the problem? Tell them to observe Jewish laws, rituals, and festivals. If you say they will refuse, this doesn't require them to reject their Islamic faith; they just need to pretend to act like Jews. And Islam is already full of strict laws like prohibiting pork, praying three times a day, and observing Ramadan, most of which are compatible with Judaism. If you say that Muslims are stubborn and won't agree, then I hope you consider whether it is shameless for a country that has never even thought of embracing them to say such a thing. I am writing this assuming that the definition of secular Judaism is correct. I am not arguing that you are not Jewish because you have deviated from traditional Judaism. However, the crucial point here is that your current definition of a Jew must inevitably embrace Palestinians who observe all Jewish laws and festivals and have Jewish ancestry. You will argue that they will refuse to do so. However, this has nothing to do with their beliefs. Palestinian Muslims and Christians will maintain all their traditions and creeds. They will simply additionally maintain Jewish traditions. In that case, you will argue that they cannot even accept those. However, they already observe strict Islamic laws. And many of the contents of Jewish law and the regulations of Islamic law overlap. Therefore, their

burden is relatively small. Furthermore, if this removes the justification for all the discrimination they face, and if it allows them to gain advantages in the Jewish community or prevents them from being ignored as outsiders, a significant number are likely to do so. In that case, you will criticize how they can maintain their beliefs while observing all Jewish traditions. However, you already have many secular atheist Jews who observe all Jewish traditions without believing in any central Jewish creed. Observing traditions and abandoning or having a creed are entirely separate matters.